

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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XORIJIY TAJRIBA**

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KIRISH SO‘ZI

HURMATLI ANJUMAN ISHTIROKCHILARI, MEHMONLAR, HAMKASBLAR, AZIZ TALABALAR!

Sizlarni Toshkent menejment va iqtisodiyot instituti tomonidan tashkil etilayotgan mazkur Respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumanida qutlashdan mamnunmiz.

Qadrli anjuman ishtirokchilari, bugun biz mamlakatimizda biznesni qo‘llab-quvvatlash va iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish masalalari bo‘yicha amalga oshirilayotgan ishlar, mavjud muammolar va ularni bartaraf etish yo‘llari, hamda bu yo‘nalishdagi xorijiy tajribalarni muhokama qilish uchun to‘plandik.

Habaringiz bor, Prezidentimiz tomonidan 2024-yilni O‘zbekistonda “Yoshlar va biznesni qo‘llab-quvvatlash yili”, deb e‘lon qilinganida, inson qadrini ulug‘lash va aholimiz manfaatlarini ta‘minlash uchun kuchli iqtisodiyot barpo etish asosiy vazifalarimizdan biri ekanligi ta‘kidlangan edi.

Shunga ko‘ra, joriy yilda iqtisodiyotimizga xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etishga, tadbirkorlik va xususiy mulk uchun keng imkoniyatlar yaratishga, ilm-fan, innovatsiya, IT kabi sohalarni, “yashil” va raqamli texnologiyalarni rivojlantirishga alohida e‘tibor qaratilmoqda.

Chunki, barqaror va kuchli iqtisodiyot nafaqat iqtisodiyot subyektlari uchun, balki jamiyatimizning kelajagi va farovonligi uchun ham juda katta ahamiyatga ega.

Hozirgi kunda, bizning jamiyatimiz - raqamli transformatsiya davriga qadam qo‘ydi. Raqamlashtirish jarayoni - biznes jarayonlaridan tortib, davlat xizmatlariga qadar ko‘plab sohalarni qamrab olmoqda.

Albatta bunday o‘zgarishlar, texnologik taraqqiyotga hamohang ravishda, qo‘shimcha imkoniyatlarni ochishga va rivojlanishning yangi strategiyalarini ishlab chiqishga keng imkoniyatlar yaratmoqda.

Lekin shu bilan bir qatorda, iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish va bunday sharoitda biznesni rivojlantirish jarayonlarida, o‘ziga xos muammolar va turli savollar ham yuzaga kelmoqda.

Bunday masalalarni o‘rganib, uning yechimlarini topish uchun Toshkent menejment va iqtisodiyot institutining professor-o‘qituvchilari tomonidan ham turli ilmiy tadqiqotlarni olib borish yo‘lga qo‘yilgan. Ularning tadqiqotlari natijalaridan - o‘quv jarayonlarida, ta‘lim sifatini oshirish maqsadlarida, keng foydalaniladi.

Bu o‘z navbatida, institutda menejment, iqtisodiyot va axborot texnologiyalari sohasida tayyorlanadigan malakali mutaxassislarining nafaqat nazariy bilimlarini, balki amaliy ko‘nikmalarini ham oshirishga hizmat qiladi.

Bundan tashqari, institutda innovatsion dasturlar va loyihalar orqali talabalarni yangi texnologiyalar bilan tanishtirish, ularda raqamli iqtisodiyot va global biznes muhitida raqobatbardosh bo‘lish uchun zarur bo‘lgan ko‘nikmalarni shakllantirishga yordam beradi.

Bugungi anjumanda, biz raqamlashtirish va biznesni rivojlantirish jarayonlarida uchraydigan muammolarni chuqur o‘rganishni va ilmiy asoslangan yechimlarni izlashni o‘z oldimizga maqsad qilib qo‘yganmiz.

Shu bilan birga, asosiy anjuman va sho‘ba yig‘ilishlarida mazkur masalalar bo‘yicha xorijiy tajribalarni ham tahlil qilish orqali, biz qanday yechimlar topishimiz mumkinligini muhokama qilamiz.

Bugun sizlarning e‘tiboringizga taqdim etiladigan taqdimotlar va fikrlar - bizni zamonaviy iqtisodiyotning yangi talablariga mos keladigan biznes modellarni yaratishga ilhomlantiradi.

Maqsadimiz – bu kabi ilmiy-amaliy uchrashuvlar orqali ilm ahlini va biznes vakillarini bir joyda jamlab, biznesni qo‘llab-quvvatlash mexanizmlarini hamda iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish jarayonlarini yanada takomillashtirish bo‘yicha asoslangan takliflar va amaliy tavsiyalarni ishlab chiqishga imkoniyatlar yaratishdan iboratdir.

Biz bu jarayonda, o‘z tajribamizni almashish va birgalikda muammolarni hal qilish uchun yangi g‘oyalarni kashf etishni maqsad qilamiz.

Umid qilamanki, anjumanimiz samarali va foydali bo‘ladi.

Har biringizning ishtirokingiz va hissangiz bu jarayonda juda muhim.

Keling, birgalikda yangiliklarga ochiq bo‘lib, innovatsion yechimlarni izlaylik!

Bugungi anjuman ishiga va unda ishtirok etayotgan barcha ishtirokchilarning ilmiy-ijodiy faoliyatlariga ulkan muvaffaqiyatlar tilaymiz!

**Axmedov Xojiakbarxon Dilshatovich,
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5-SHO'BA.

BIZNES VA BOSHQARUVDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT HAMDA SUN'IY INTELLEKT TEXNOLOGIYALARI

HISTORY OF DEVELOPMENT AND CURRENT STATE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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Abstract: The article presents a philosophical analysis of the history of artificial intelligence (AI) and examines its value for modern individuals and society. By uncovering the ideological, technological, and economic specifics of the first "AI winter," which lasted from the early 1970s to the mid-2000s, the article emphasizes that current technological trends and ongoing developments showcase the successful progress in AI. This stage in the history of AI (starting from the second half of the 2000s) is referred to as the "new spring" of artificial intelligence.

Key words: Artificial intelligence, computer systems, algorithms, Turing, expert systems, computing power, big data, machine learning, human rights, history, technological progress.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada sun'iy intellekt tarixi hodisasining falsafiy tahlili keltirilgan va uning zamonaviy inson va jamiyat uchun ahamiyati muhokama qilinadi. Maqolada 1970-yillarning boshidan 2000-yillarning o'rtalarigacha davom etgan sun'iy intellektning birinchi "qishining" g'oyaviy, texnologik va iqtisodiy o'ziga xosliklari ochib berilgan holda, zamonaviy texnologik tendensiyalar va davom etayotgan o'zgarishlar sun'iy intellekt sohasining muvaffaqiyatli rivojlanishidan dalolat berishi ta'kidlanadi. O'rganilayotgan hodisa tarixidagi bu bosqich (2000-yillarning ikkinchi yarmidan boshlab) sun'iy intellektning "yangi bahori" deb ataladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Sun'iy intellekt, kompyuter tizimlari, algoritmlar, Tyuring, ekspert tizimlar, hisoblash quvvati, katta hajmdagi ma'lumotlar, mashinalashtirilgan ta'lim, inson huquqlari, tarix, texnologik jarayon.

Аннотация: В статье представлен философский анализ феномена истории искусственного интеллекта и рассматривается вопрос о его значении для современного человека и общества. Раскрывая идеологическую, технологическую и экономическую специфику первой "зимы искусственного интеллекта," длившейся с начала 1970-х до середины 2000-х годов, в статье отмечается, что современные технологические тенденции и происходящие разработки свидетельствуют об успешном развитии сферы искусственного интеллекта. Этот этап в истории изучаемого явления (со второй половины 2000-х годов) назван "новой весной искусственного интеллекта."

Ключевые слова: Искусственный интеллект, компьютерные системы, алгоритмы, Тьюринг, экспертные системы, вычислительная мощность, большие данные, машинное обучение, права человека, история, технологический прогресс.

The Development of Artificial Intelligence: A Historical Overview

In the 1980s, scientists Barr and Feigenbaum proposed a seminal definition of artificial intelligence (AI) as a field of computer science dedicated to developing intelligent computer systems. This definition remains largely unchanged, as AI systems are distinguished by their ability to mimic human cognitive functions such as speech and foreign language recognition, learning, and reasoning. AI is now characterized by software systems and algorithms capable of solving problems in ways similar to humans. However, the development of AI technologies required a significant historical journey, reflecting its foundation as a fundamental science with a rich history.

The concept of AI can be succinctly encapsulated by the phrase "Spirit in the Machine," emphasizing the synthesis of mechanical and cognitive capabilities rather than their separate development.

Early Foundations in the 20th Century

In the early 20th century, science fiction introduced the idea of artificially intelligent robots, inspiring subsequent scientific exploration. By the 1950s, a generation of scientists, mathematicians, and philosophers sought to unlock the technologies necessary for AI development. Alan Turing, a pioneering British polymath, laid the groundwork for AI by proposing that machines could emulate human problem-solving and decision-making processes. In his influential 1950 paper, "Computing Machinery and Intelligence," Turing detailed the principles for building intelligent machines and suggested a framework for evaluating their capabilities, now famously known as the Turing Test.

Early AI Programs and Research Milestones

In 1955, the field witnessed significant progress with the creation of the **Logic Theorist** by Allen Newell, Cliff Shaw, and Herbert Simon. Funded by the RAND Corporation, this program mimicked human problem-solving abilities and is often regarded as the first true AI program. The **Logic Theorist** was unveiled during the Dartmouth Summer Research Project on Artificial Intelligence (DSRPAI) in 1956, organized by Joseph McCarthy and Marvin Minsky, marking the formal birth of AI as a discipline.

Growth and Challenges (1957–1974)

From 1957 to 1974, AI research flourished, driven by improvements in computing power, data storage, and accessibility. Machine learning algorithms advanced, and researchers developed a deeper understanding of their applications. However, the burgeoning field faced significant challenges, particularly the inadequacy of computing power. The limited speed and capacity of computers made it difficult to process and store the vast amounts of information required for tasks such as natural language processing. Hans Moravec, a student of John McCarthy, highlighted the limitations of the era, stating that “computers were still too weak to be intelligent.”

As progress slowed, enthusiasm waned, and funding for AI research diminished. For nearly a decade, the field advanced only marginally, marking a period of stagnation often referred to as the “AI winter.” Despite these setbacks, the foundational work during this time paved the way for the subsequent resurgence of AI in the late 20th and early 21st centuries.

Advancements in Artificial Intelligence: Key Developments and Challenges

The Problem of Logical Thinking and Theorem Proving

A central challenge in modeling logical thinking within AI is the automation of theorem proving. Since the 1960s, various programs have been developed to find theorem proofs. According to J. McCarthy, a leading American AI specialist, these programs exhibit “common sense,” reflecting their capacity to generate deductive solutions.

The 1980s Revival of Artificial Intelligence

The 1980s marked a revival of AI, driven by two major advancements: the expansion of algorithmic tools and the availability of increased computational resources. During this period, John Hopfield and David Rumelhart popularized “deep learning” techniques, enabling computers to learn from experience. Simultaneously, Edward Feigenbaum introduced **expert systems**, designed to emulate the decision-making processes of human experts. These systems relied on domain experts to provide insights into various scenarios, allowing non-experts to receive expert-level guidance through the system. Expert systems found extensive applications in industrial settings.

The Japanese government played a pivotal role during this era by funding AI research under its **Fifth Generation Computer Project (FGCP)**. From 1982 to 1990, \$400 million was invested to revolutionize data processing, introduce logic programming, and improve AI technologies. While many of the project’s ambitious goals were unmet, its indirect effects were profound, inspiring a new generation of engineers and scientists. Despite this, the FGCP funding ceased, and AI once again faded from prominence.

The Quiet Flourishing of AI in the 1990s and 2000s

Ironically, during periods of reduced government funding and publicity, AI research thrived. Many key goals were achieved in the 1990s and 2000s. A landmark achievement occurred in 1997 when IBM’s **Deep Blue** defeated reigning world chess champion Garry Kasparov. This victory signaled the arrival of AI systems capable of outperforming human experts in specific domains.

This progress was not due to revolutionary changes in AI coding but rather advancements in computational power. The memory limitations that hindered AI for decades were resolved. As per **Moore’s Law** (1965), proposed by Gordon Moore, computing power and memory capacity double approximately every year. By the late 1990s, computer systems had surpassed these limitations, allowing AI systems like Deep Blue to excel.

Moore’s Law and the Rollercoaster of AI Development

The cyclical progress of AI, marked by periods of rapid achievement followed by stagnation, can be explained through the interplay of technological saturation and Moore’s Law. Scientists continually push AI capabilities to the limits of existing computing power (data storage and processing speed). Once these limits are reached, further advancements in AI await corresponding improvements in computational resources. This phenomenon explains milestones such as Deep Blue’s triumph in 1997 and Google’s **AlphaGo** defeating Chinese Go champion Qi Jie in 2017.

The Era of Big Data and AI Applications

We are currently experiencing the “big data” era, characterized by the ability to collect and analyze massive amounts of information that surpass human processing capabilities. Artificial intelligence (AI) plays a pivotal role in managing and leveraging this data across various industries, including technology, banking, marketing, and entertainment. AI benefits from the synergy of vast data availability and powerful computing resources,

even when algorithmic improvements are minimal. The growth in data continues unabated, even as Moore's Law—which predicts the doubling of computing power approximately every two years—shows signs of slowing. Breakthroughs in computer science, mathematics, and neuroscience hold the potential to overcome these technological ceilings.

Global Trends in AI and Machine Learning Projects (2015–2017)

The number of AI and machine learning projects experienced exponential growth between 2015 and 2017. In 2015, only 17 AI initiatives were announced by major companies, while the first half of 2017 alone saw 74 new projects. Over three years, 162 AI projects were recorded across 28 countries and 20 industries. Notably, 85% of these initiatives were fully implemented, while the remaining 15% were either planned or in pilot stages. These projects spanned all industries except government agencies, with large businesses accounting for 85% of the clientele for such initiatives.

Recommendations for Ethical and Effective AI Deployment

To ensure the responsible and ethical deployment of AI systems, the following recommendations are proposed:

Adopt Human Rights Impact Assessments (HRIAs):

Introduce legislation and regulations mandating the conduct of HRIAs for AI systems that are developed, acquired, or implemented by government agencies.

Retrospective and Prospective HRIAs:

Conduct HRIAs for all AI systems currently in use by government agencies as soon as relevant legislation is enacted. For future systems, HRIAs should be completed prior to their acquisition or development.

Lifecycle Monitoring and Continuous Assessment:

Regularly monitor the human rights impact of AI systems throughout their lifecycle. Conduct HRIAs at each significant phase and whenever the system's context, scope, or objectives undergo substantial changes.

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